

The Challenges and Needs of Animal Welfare Inspectors on Farm and at Slaughter:

An Ethnographic Study of Animal Welfare Inspection in Ireland, Denmark, France, and Poland

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1 Summary

Drawing on fieldwork in four European countries, this project aims to identify the training needs of inspectors by examining the challenges they face in the conduct of their work, with a focus on assessing welfare on farm and at slaughter. The report concludes by providing recommendations based on these insights as to how EURCAW can support their work.

Recommendations include:

- Interview-based podcast discussing topics of inspection with inspectors discussing challenges and how to address them, on farm, at transport, and at slaughter
- Direct contact to the regional offices as well as the head offices to promote EURCAW - Pigs
- More literature on sow welfare, indicators of fitness at transport, transport regulations, and conditions of housing pigs in stalls at lairage both overnight and for shorter periods – such as research on temperature, stocking density, and mixing.
- Comprehensive study of how inspection is performed across all European countries as all inspectors expressed an interest in understanding how inspection is implemented in other European countries.
- More fieldwork focused on transport checks as these were not possible to fully incorporate into this project, but transport was consistently mentioned by inspectors as an area associated with significant risks to welfare.
- Greater provision of materials and literature on conflict resolution, resilience training, and communication strategies.

Ethnographic research methods examine the lived experience of participants and as such, involve participant observation where the researcher joins participants in their daily activities. Insights from participant observation are then incorporated into follow-up semi-structured interviews which include open questions allowing further elaboration of insights from participant observation. Much of my work with inspectors was mainly observation of their work with limited participation in duties of animal welfare assessment. Due to EURCAW – Pigs' use of photographic material in our literature, I also photographed the work of inspectors where such access was granted.

2 Introduction

In the daily labour of welfare assessment, inspectors are faced with challenges that complicate the task of regulation. The challenges are multifaceted and complex, ranging from the opacity of legislation to communication issues (Väärikkälä et al., 2020). Despite these challenges, Veissier et al. (2021) highlight the importance of the inspector for improving welfare on farms as they are pivotal to communicating the legislation to farmers and motivating farmers to comply (Anneberg et al, 2013; Overstreet & Anneberg, 2019). Crucially, Veissier et al. (2021) note how it is the inspector rather than the inspection that influences negative perceptions in farmers (see also Anneberg et al., 2012) and conclude that exchanging experiences between farmers and inspectors and more practical training for inspectors would reinforce inspector confidence and expertise.

Its population of 150 million pigs makes the EU pig sector the largest livestock category in the European Union (Augère-Granier, 2020). Despite the varying scales of production across the four countries, only 1% of farms are inspected annually and an even smaller percentage of these visits are solely animal welfare visits. The fieldwork involved joining inspectors at inspections specifically targeted at tail docking (Ireland) as well as cross-compliance inspections (Denmark and Poland). EU Regulations require that 1% of all beneficiaries of EU subsidies are selected for full Cross Compliance inspections (DAFM, 2021a). In 2018, the European Parliamentary Research Service (Augère-Granier, 2020) detailed how ‘almost three quarters of the EU's pigs were being reared in six EU Member States: Spain (20.8 %), Germany (17.8 %), France (9.3 %), Denmark (8.5 %), the Netherlands (8.1 %) and Poland (7.4 %)’. I will provide a brief overview of the pig sector in the four selected countries to give an insight into the types of challenges that inspectors face.

2.1 The Irish Pig Sector

The 2021 Crop and Livestock Survey estimates the total pig population in Ireland to be 1.6 million pigs including over 150,000 breeding sows (Emerson et al, 2022). The largest number of pigs are concentrated along the Northern Ireland border counties. There is a marked trend toward larger farms and consolidation of herds. In 2020, total exports were estimated by Bord Bia to be €541 million (Duggan, 2022). The Department of Agriculture, Food, and the Marine launched their Animal Welfare Strategy 2021 – 2025 “Working Together for Animal Welfare” in which they specifically mention the need to support the sector in reducing the need for tail docking of pigs and incorporate animal-based indicators into animal welfare assessments of pigs as well as support the development of high-welfare outdoor-reared pigs (DAFM, 2021b). The sector is regulated by veterinary inspectors located across sixteen regional offices in the country, where a head vet manages a team of veterinary inspectors.

2.2 The Danish Pig Sector

Over 62% of Danish land is dedicated to agriculture (Nielsen, 2021) whilst the country itself is home to a population of 13.1 million pigs (Danish Agriculture and Food Council, 2021). The majority of pig farming occurs in Central and Northern Jutland. Over 90% of Danish pig production is exported (Danish Agriculture and Food Council, 2021). Intensification of Danish pig production means almost ‘97% of pigs are kept on farms with 1,000 or more animals’ (Augère-Granier, 2020) with Denmark having the largest number of commercial holdings in the EU with an average of 4,700 pigs per holding. Today, more than 73% of Denmark’s pig population are in herds of more than 5,000 pigs (Danish Agriculture and Food Council, 2021). Animal welfare inspections on cross compliance (*krydsoverensstemmelse*) with EU legislation are carried out by inspectors from the Danish Agricultural Agency (*Landbrugsstyrelsen*) (LBST, 2022) whilst random and prioritized inspections on farm are coordinated by the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (*Fødevarestyrelsen*) (DG Sante, 2021). DAA has three central administrations and four decentralized district offices (DG Sante (2021).

2.3 The Polish Pig Sector

Poland has sixteen districts with the majority of pig production occurs in Greater Poland (*Wielkopolskie*) in central Poland (DG Sante, 2018). With a pig population of 10.2 million in 2021 (Eurostat, 2021), just under

fifty percent of Poland’s land is dedicated to agriculture. Poland produces 7.4% of Europe’s pigs but the industry has faced continues challenges since the emergence of African Swine Fever in 2014. Unlike Denmark, Ireland, and France, where over 90% of pig farms are home to herds of more than 400 pigs, over 60% of Polish farms are classed as small units (Bellini, 2021) with the inspectors informing me that there are over 72,000 pig herds in the country. Whilst Poland exported approx. 411,000 tons in 2021 (Rolnika, 2022) and count Slovakia and Germany as their main exporting countries, the country is the second highest importer of live pigs in Europe. In 2019, they imported 6.8 million pigs mainly from Denmark (Levitt, 2020).

2.4 The French Pig Sector

France is the third largest producer of pigs in Europe following Spain and German. Of the 389,000 farms in France, 37.3% are dedicated to livestock farming (French Ministry of Agriculture and Food, 2020). In line with widespread trends across Europe, the agricultural landscape shows clear signs of consolidation as larger farms (those farms generating more than €250,000 per year standard output) now account for 40% of the agricultural land (French Ministry of Agriculture and Food, 2020). The Agricultural Census 2020 identifies 20,000 farms dedicated to pigs and poultry and it is estimated that around 10,000 of these farms are pig farms home to a population of 23.2 million pigs (French Ministry of Agriculture and Food, 2020, LePorc, 2020). Three quarters of these farms are located in the Grand West, specifically the regions of Brittany, Loire Valley, and Normandy (Augère-Granier, 2020). France exports slightly more than it imports with the main exporting destinations located in Germany and Italy and mainly importing from Spain (Hivernat, 2015).

3 Methods

An ethnographic study is characterized by a number of methods designed to give the researcher an insight into the everyday routines, practices, and activities of participants. A primary method is participant observation where a researcher both observes and participates to gain an insight into the life of a community or group. The degree of participation or the extent of observation can vary widely depending on the context of the fieldwork. Therefore, participant observation is frequently accompanied by semi-structured or open interviews that enable a deeper exploration of the way that participants view the world, negotiate the challenges they face, and understand themselves in relation to others. Such a grounded approach makes space for the participants to guide the research, as it is through their words and actions that the researcher gains an understanding of a specific context.

Figure 3.1: Assessment at a large commercial farm (© E. Mc Loughlin)

Due to the specialized nature of animal welfare inspection, observation was the primary mode of engagement in the field. I joined inspectors at work, almost in an apprentice role, asking questions and following their routines to understand their work, their background, and the challenges they encounter. Through informal conversations and follow-up interviews, I examined the key challenges they identified in their work. Through open-ended questions, I facilitated a reflective and exploratory discussion.

3.1 Rationale

The rationale for this qualitative approach is two-fold. This research emerged from numerous unsuccessful attempts to cultivate dialogue with inspectors so to understand the challenges of animal welfare inspection. Quantitative instruments like questionnaires proved unsuccessful due to poor uptake and an unestablished network. The face-to-face engagement of ethnography makes possible a relationship of trust and openness between the researcher and the participant so that sensitive topics can be discussed with ease. This is typically realized through a continued dialogue with participants and thus, I hope that this is just the beginning of a long-term relationship with the participants in this study and that this work can be developed further.

3.2 Practicalities

In total, whilst I contacted over fifty individuals, I secured twenty-six participants across the four countries – six in Ireland, eight in Denmark, seven in France, and five in Poland. The EURCAW Work Programme set out that the project would include 2-3 inspectors operating across on farm, at transport, and at slaughter with a variety of experience levels. However, due to the relative separation between inspectors who work at slaughter and those working on farm, these figures doubled due to the nature of the work.

I conducted twenty-six semi-structured interviews, including four group interviews. These interviews ranged from fifty minutes to four hours. Five of these interviews were carried out online, some prior to participant observation to organize the visit and some following my visit to their workplace. In total, I visited eleven field-sites across the four countries including five farms and six slaughterhouses. Often, inspectors offered to collect me to bring me to their workplace and they often rearranged their tasks to make time to discuss their work with me. I am very grateful for the generosity of their time.

In addition to this, I attended an online Better Training for Safer Food course on ‘Animal Welfare in Pig Production’. This three-day course not only gave me critical insights into evaluations of welfare but also made it possible to establish links with inspectors working in other member states with a view to future contacts and potential research.

3.3 Logistical Challenges

This project faced several critical challenges. On a macro scale, these challenges include the continued effects of the COVID-19 pandemic across the four European countries, the Russian war on Ukraine which would lead to heightened pressure on the Polish authorities as well as to wider uncertainty about travel, and the narrow window of time that was available to plan, contact, coordinate, and conduct the fieldwork which involved at least two field-sites in each country, sometimes three. These challenges were

exacerbated by numerous micro-scale obstacles such as identifying the right people who coordinate inspections across four member states. Furthermore, local level challenges such as avian influenza in France meant that it was not possible to visit a farm in France as pig farm inspections were temporarily halted, so that resources could be redirected to the culling of a bird population in the area.

Nevertheless, familiarity and established contacts in Denmark facilitated a relatively quick coordination of fieldwork here and a prompt response from Ireland made organization of fieldwork in late February possible. Furthermore, in both Ireland and Denmark, language barriers were not a problem as I am a native English speaker and am proficient in Danish. However, unestablished networks in both France and Poland would significantly slow down progress. Whilst a conversational level in French enabled a ‘breaking of the ice’, the contacts in France and Poland had to find inspectors who were comfortable to speak to me in English. If there was more time available, a translator would have made their work easier and could have made it possible to include longer-serving inspectors in both France and Poland. However, the experience level ranged from less than a year to ten years’ experience in both countries, so the project succeeded in accessing a cross-section of experience across all four states.

3.4 Fieldsites

Month	Country Visited	No. of Inspectors at each site visit*	Fieldsite Visited
February	<i>Denmark</i>	1	Commercial pig slaughterhouse (Killing 35,000 pigs per week)
	<i>Denmark</i>	3	Commercial pig farm
	<i>Ireland</i>	2	Commercial pig farm (Intact Tails Visit)
		1	Industrial pig slaughterhouse (Killing 4,500 pigs a day)
		2	Commercial pig farm (Intact Tails Visit)
March	<i>Denmark</i>	3	Industrial sow slaughterhouse (Killing 6,200 sows per week)
April	<i>Poland</i>	2	Commercial pig farm (Up to 1,000 pigs)
		Same 2 +	Industrial pig slaughterhouse (Killing 2,000 pigs a day)

		2 resident inspectors	
		2	Traditional mixed species farm (47 sows / 166 piglets / 250 pigs for fattening / one boar)
	France	3	Farm visit cancelled – Group interview (Two inspectors working with pig inspection and one with cattle and sheep)
		2	Commercial pig slaughterhouse (Killing over 3,000-3,500 pigs a day)
		2	Commercial pig slaughterhouse (Killing over 2,500 pigs a day)

**Note: Whilst I met more inspectors at certain sites than the main participants in the research, I have only counted those with whom I had a conversation about the project and their responses to challenges they face in their role.*

3.5 Participant Profiles

One key aim of the project was to achieve a relatively good range of experiences across the on farm and at slaughter inspection by engaging with inspectors who have a varied range of work experience. However, rather than providing a table detailing the background and experience of inspectors that might make their identities more readily recognizable amongst their peers, I have chosen to provide an overview of this information in the following points.

In total, I interviewed 26 participants, four of whom work in the coordination of welfare inspections and were not observed in the field. The remaining 22 were working as inspectors and I conducted participant observation with 17 of these participants.

- There were thirteen female participants and nine male participants.
- Twelve participants worked in on farm inspection and the remaining ten worked at slaughter.
- Number of participants with
 - Less than or equal to 3 years' experience - 9
 - More than three but less than or equal to ten years' experience - 4
 - More than ten years' experience – 6
 - More than twenty years' experience - 3
- Of the 22 participants, thirteen are qualified veterinarians and the remaining nine have animal science qualifications except three who have background in agriculture and/or slaughterhouse work.

4 The Landscape of Inspection

4.1 Why Become an Inspector

Understanding why participants became inspectors conveys the value they place on different aspects of the job while also revealing whether the reason they decided to become an inspector is aligned with the reality of the occupation. Across the four countries, the most popular reason amongst the participants for becoming an inspector was the predictable working hours. The majority of the participants were qualified veterinarians who had left the arduous long hours of practice for a position that improved their work-life balance, as it was a Monday to Friday job that was well paid. Those participants who were educated in animal science had worked in private industry and felt that the working hours and workload was more manageable, and the work was described as more fulfilling. Specifically for the inspectors in Poland, the permanent nature of the employment offered job security that was particularly important. It was also important for them to use their qualifications in animal science.

Another important reason cited by a number of inspectors in France specifically was the desire to improve animal welfare problems that they had witnessed in their experience working in slaughterhouses. One inspector described the desire to make a difference and improve the quality of life of animals when it matters, when they are alive. He described how ‘Like I wanted to improve the condition of animals, that is what I’m interested in. If I worked in industry, it would be very difficult because you don’t have much power.’ (2022). When I asked does he feel empowered in his role, he shared how, ‘We don’t have a lot of power, but we have the tools to improve conditions’ (2022). This desire to make a difference was noted by another French inspector who admitted that she had not planned to work as a slaughterhouse inspector but that she gets a sense of fulfillment from making a difference. This inspector had initially chosen to work as an inspector based on the varied nature of the work and the numerous career pathways that a qualified inspector can take in France, from farm and slaughter inspection to administration and governmental roles. The varied nature of the work was similarly praised by one Danish inspector as giving them freedom to manage their workload. When asked about the best part of the job, they responded.

‘Freedom! There’s so much freedom in the job. There is no-one telling me what to do. I have a list of tasks that I need to accomplish, and I decide what kind of a day I want. So if I just want to do a little visit, I can do a half day and drive somewhere and it’s my decision.’ (2022)

Many of the Danish inspectors appreciated the variety of the role both on farm and at slaughter as inspectors would be involved in welfare assessment as well as report-writing and quality checking.

Figure 4.1.1: Inspector assessing pigs during an unannounced inspection (© E. Mc Loughlin)

4.2 Experiences of Training

Training experiences are based on the insights from participants and their experiences and is not based on a comprehensive of the official training courses in the member states. Such a review could be insightful as the inspectors described varying degrees of training courses. The French inspectors appeared to be the most satisfied with their training experiences. Indeed, the French route appears to have the most comprehensive training programme with one participant describing their two-year education at the higher education research institute VetAgro Sup in Lyon as equipping them with a variety of skills in animal welfare assessment. Two of the French inspectors are undergoing on-the-job training towards becoming an animal welfare inspector both on farm and at slaughter, which typically lasts two years. Therefore, in France, there is no requirement to have an animal-based background but inspectors who train on-the-job (termed a *functionnaire*) must pass an exam where they are assessed by a senior inspector before they can perform inspections alone.

Denmark, Poland, and Ireland did not have specific training courses associated with higher education institutions. However in Ireland, all inspectors are qualified veterinarians who apply for a position in the department. Once successful, they participate in an induction, attend training courses in the department and can also complete further courses at higher education institutions once they are related to their work but are typically trained by other inspectors. Whilst qualified veterinarians are eligible to work as inspectors in both Denmark and Poland, the minimum requirement is a qualification or background in agriculture or animal science. Across Denmark, Poland, and Ireland, all training is provided by the employer in various forms from mandatory training to side-by-side peer training. There is also the opportunity to access BTSF training. In Poland, there is a tiered system where one starts out as a junior inspector and graduates to a senior inspector role, however insights from the Polish inspectors suggest that this elevation in status appears to be determined by budgetary constraints rather than experience.

Participants across the four countries have participated in both in-person and online courses provided by their regional and national departments. All inspectors were familiar and/or had participated in a BTSF training course. Yet, many inspectors admitted that frequently training did not match the reality of what they were confronted with on farm and at slaughter. Furthermore, certain inspectors expressed an interest in further training about assessing welfare problems and a course on welfare itself. Inspectors at slaughter across the four countries remarked how shift-work in slaughterhouses impacted their ability to participate in training courses. Indeed, experiences of training at slaughter were quite varied with one inspector admitting, 'I received six weeks training but otherwise there's no training.' They added then that there are BTSF courses but that they are especially interested in animal welfare as a concept and indicators for assessment, adding that whilst vets may be the best poised to evaluate welfare, there's still a need for general welfare training. Several inspectors mentioned BTSF training, but the overall impression is that there are areas where the inspectors need more support. Areas like assessing welfare at slaughter, sow welfare, and calibration across inspectors were all cited as areas where they would be interested in more training (see 6.2 Training Needs and Resources). The slaughterhouse inspectors mentioned how side-by-side training was how they were trained which meant that the culture of who they took over from was important for how progressive animal welfare assessment can be at slaughter.

On farm inspectors in France shared how there is a good range of training courses available to them, both in person and online. Interestingly, they noted that there were many training courses on biosecurity measures in light of the threat of ASF that covered topics like legislation and that some of these courses included farmers. Yet, they remarked how the fact that the same approach was not adopted with animal welfare suggests that welfare is not prioritized to the same degree as biosecurity. Furthermore, one inspector described how including farmers on training courses assisted with building a shared dialogue and common understanding of legislation and could be useful for animal welfare initiatives. As the farmer-inspector-animal encounter on the farm is critical to shaping perceptions of welfare, then having experiences of discussing welfare in a neutral space, not on the territory of either the farmer or the inspector, can benefit the open dialogue between inspectors and farmers. Training courses like this will also work to prioritize welfare. Similarly, a French inspector at slaughter believed that animal welfare was not prioritized in France and whilst they praised the offering of BTSF, they did say that some of their topics are too broad. ‘I think the animal welfare training in France is not enough. Animal welfare is not a priority but with the association L214 [Animal Rights Organization involved in undercover recording of animal cruelty in France] now Ministers are saying it is a priority. It’s a new objective. There is not enough training, the manager is doing training for the agents.’ They went on to say that the ‘problem in France is that there is no harmonization in the different departments even in the different abattoirs, so there are some vets who don’t have enough stunning training. They can’t transmit to the technicians in their abattoir.’ Furthermore, this same inspector identified animal welfare as the main challenge to their role. This reflects the importance of greater support for inspectors and more clarity, ‘I think its animal welfare. Pathology is easy, that is no problem, I mean I know an abscess and inspection of a slaughterhouse is no problem. The real problem is animal welfare because it’s hard for the business operators and operatives to understand what we want and what we don’t want. The training of operatives is not our job – they must have a certificate of competence. But we don’t exactly want the same thing. Sometimes we receive agents [slaughterhouse staff] who know nothing about animal welfare.’

Thus, understanding the non-standardized pathways to becoming an animal welfare inspector across the member states conveys the differentiation of training needs and experiences, where some states would benefit from a more general grounding in animal welfare assessment whilst others would prefer more specific and focused materials covering a range of topics. The use of side-by-side training is appreciated as essential to calibration but also has the potential to reproduce certain standards of welfare. Thus, having a point of contact with expertise in certain areas such as legislation or animal welfare indicators could cultivate a culture of open dialogue and calibration (see 6.5 Working with Other Inspectors).

4.3 Contested Identity of the Animal Welfare Inspector

A 2019 study into the challenges and opportunities in animal welfare in pig farming in France detailed how the movement from an advisory role to strict regulation was under-resourced, with veterinary inspectors noting how the lack of resources meant limited controls were taking place. This same report noted how farmers feared over-regulation whilst inspectors highlighted the disparity between enforcement across different departments (Ceccantini, 2017). This shift in identity from a pastoral to a policing position puts a strain on communication and dialogue during the inspection encounter on farms and at slaughter which can be an obstacle to resolving welfare issues. This tension between motivating farmers and enforcing rules complicates the inspection encounter and can position the inspector and the farmer on opposing sides (5,24).

The inspectors in France clearly identified how their desired role was that of a teacher to farmers during inspection but due to increased regulation and legislation, they were now perceived as the police of agriculture. Another French inspector noted how assuming a police role was not conducive to healthy workplace relations with economic operators. Working as an inspector at slaughter, they faced a number of challenges in communicating their role to the slaughterhouse as they were perceived as working to close down their facility. Instead, this inspector developed a pedagogical approach, where cooperation relies on viewing problems of welfare as

Figure 4.3.1: Inspectors at slaughter overseeing the herding of pigs (© E. Mc Loughlin)

obstacles to be overcome rather than failings of work procedures. However, such a perspective is certainly not shared by all inspectors, and it is clear here that inspectors working at slaughter have a different set of challenges to those conducting on farm inspection. Where inspectors on farm must negotiate the emotional labour of dealing with the personal problems of farmers that they really don't want to have to deal with, inspectors at slaughter must find a way to make their regulatory role bearable in the workplace. This involves finding a way to work that works for the individual as well as the workplace. Approaches can range from a more clear-cut distanced approach to a view that inspection is a collaboration working towards a common goal of better welfare.

Inspectors across all four countries expressed an awareness that economic operators like farmers, slaughterhouse workers, and companies, as well as transporters, may try to hide practices from them. It was amidst this awareness that inspectors legitimized the necessity of their role in the landscape of pig production as essential to ensuring that regulations are followed. However, inspectors find a way to accept that economic operators may try to hide practices from an inspector but believe that the presence of inspectors makes a difference to how operators think about welfare and crucially, how they treat pigs.

'I think if there is nobody to look that they could sometimes use the electric prod more than they have to, things like that, but I think the fact that we are there with them every day, we speak with them, we give sense of what we explain, so I hope that they keep in mind, they think about that. But I don't know, when there is nobody, they will want to go faster.' (in interview, May 2022)

This comment from an inspector highlights how educating economic operators is a form of *sense-making with* rather than the *disciplining of* slaughterhouse workers in this case. This approach aligned with other attempts by inspectors to *make welfare make sense* for economic operators. However, it was achieved in different ways, from emphasizing the economic benefit to farmers to underscoring the very real threat to the industry if consumers see animals being treated poorly as well as the benefits to both workers and animals (Lin-Schilstra et al, 2022; Pinillos et al., 2016). However, several inspectors expressed frustration that

they felt compelled to *make welfare make sense*. One inspector shared how they had heard at a conference how, ‘welfare doesn’t need to be justified, it’s just this has to be done. That’s it.’ They went on to say, ‘whereas you feel like you should be demonstrating production gains, you’re trying to ... qualify it... so therein lies the problem... I’m maybe qualifying it a bit’ (2022).

There is a noticeable attempt by inspectors to minimize the considerable drain on their wellbeing that the work of inspection produces, such as qualifying their work to minimize conflict and boost consensus. Another inspector who had previously worked at a slaughterhouse, explained how they see both farmer and animal welfare as entwined. ‘If the welfare is good and work conditions are good, it is easy to have workers that stay. We can’t separate animal welfare from farmer welfare, they are in relation’ (2022). Furthermore, inspectors who were innovating a more purposeful inspection protocol for intact tails that worked towards quantifiable improvement and legal enforcement

highlighted how communication can be challenged by the wider landscape of pig farming, such as the knowledge gap between advisors and inspectors, where advisors might have a different perception of a welfare issue. For example, when inspectors identified widespread ear biting in a number of pens on a farm inspection, they were left unsatisfied by the claim that the farmer’s vet had concluded that everything was under control.

Thus, a desire to make the job more satisfying and less emotionally demanding can sometimes result in inspectors ‘picking their battles’ when it comes to welfare. Indeed, the notion of welfare issues on farms and at slaughter as numerous little battles is insightful for understanding how the individual animal is accounted for and how the group informs welfare evaluation. In one farm visit, inspectors were faced with a particular animal who was suffering considerably. The farmer explained that he had previously housed her in a hospital pen but that she was happier in a stall. Afterwards, I asked the inspectors about this sow. One inspector explained how ‘you try to advise the best you can [...] we came out to those pigs today and you’re looking at them as a group and as a group, they’re fed and watered... but there’s that one sow if you were just presented with her, you’d think that poor creature [...] I don’t think he wants to be cruel to it but it comes back to the individual animal and every animal has a right to comfort’ (2022). This balance between the individual and the group is a tension when an individual’s suffering is not indicative of the overall welfare of the group but as this inspector reflected, it is a balance between the group and the individual that ‘sometimes that does get lost a bit in our job’ (in interview, 2022).

Figure 2.3.2: On farm inspector investigating the condition of a pig in isolation (© E. Mc Loughlin)

4.4 Rapport and Dialogue

Across the four countries, all inspectors understood that the role of regulator prevents them from advising the economic operators and yet the majority of inspectors shared how they would share their opinions and experiences with those who asked for it. This was cited by those who many as being essential to building a good dialogue with farmers and cultivating a relation of cooperation in the face of demanding rules and regulation. Whilst inspectors in Ireland and France specifically referenced how farmers were interested in the insights of inspectors, Polish inspectors noted how their farmers did not want to know how it's done in other farms. However, this disinterest may

Figure 4.4.1: A farmer joins an inspector in the pens as they record the air quality (© E. Mc Loughlin)

be indicative of the discrimination that certain female inspectors experienced during visits due to their gender and age. One inspector noted how 'we might tell them what we see but the farmers here are like 'this is the best way... they don't want to hear from any other farms because they know better' (2022). The Danish inspectors on farm emphasized the importance of good dialogue, that can be hindered by the nature of unannounced cross-compliance visits. They likened an unannounced visit to being stopped by the police on the road and how such an experience immediately provokes a paranoia as to how fast you were driving. In order to alleviate this stressor, they note how taking the interaction slowly, maybe sitting with them for a few moments helps to build a rapport and eases the fears that the farmer might have. Nevertheless, Polish inspectors cited dealing with aggressive farmers as the most challenging aspect of their job and like other inspectors, they described how bringing a problem to the attention of farmers would often lead to the inspectors being the cause of the problem. They described their role as 'we don't want to make problems, we want to help to make things better.' Such an alignment of the inspector with the problem complicates the work of inspection as inspectors must balance the needs of the animal, the requirements of legislation with the people they meet and must not allow the very real challenges faced by farmers influence their evaluation.

Furthermore, despite minimizing conflict and building a rapport with economic operators, the inspector must continually reinforce their separateness through official paperwork that at times threatens the clarity of communication when dense legislative literature must be incorporated into welfare assessments. French inspectors identified this as a critical area for communication where they will explain the legislation in plain language prior to providing paperwork that is populated with legislative excerpts and legal language. The inspector's identity is continually challenged and remade by the work of inspection, moving from police enforcer to teacher to a paralegal. Furthermore, French inspectors highlighted their role in communicating changes in the legislation as part of a wider cultural shift amongst farmers. They are communicating the requirements in a way that will also make sense *of them* for the farmers and transporters, by basing the

legislation within the wider context of food security, public health, and the economic landscape. In their communication of welfare legislation to the transporters they meet at slaughter, another inspector frames changes as essential to guarantee a trustworthy food system, safe food for consumers, and critical to sustaining meat markets.

‘There is a lot of things, but I speak with them, not just about work, about their lives, but not only about the work, to know them, to understand what they do during the night, because they drive during the night and it’s not easy. We are speaking about the different truck problems and that. And after that, I am not just standing and watching, for instance, when there are some pigs which don’t want to go in... I help the worker, I help the driver, and they say *ok this guy is there to make the job easier*. After, when we talk about the future of the meat market, and the pig products, they understand that it’s very important to be clear and to work in the best way we can to be sure that there are still pigs in our place. But it takes time and drivers know, I am working with them since September, they see me one or two times in the week, I’m not just a cop.’ (May 2022)

This inspector, along with others at slaughter, demonstrates a commitment to a good dialogue with slaughterhouse operatives but another inspector was clear that it is important to maintain a distance between the inspector and the worker, and the company, for that matter. Whilst another inspector at slaughter shared how close connections with slaughterhouse workers can facilitate stronger enforcement, as workers are empowered to bring welfare issues to the attention of inspectors. Such motivational communication can however be difficult on farm when the farmer does not see the same issues as veterinary inspectors. One inspector shared how communication is challenged by the difference in perception between the farmer and the inspector. ‘We might find tail-biting behaviour in the pen, and they’ll be telling us it’s not, so there’s an education element in it to getting them to acknowledge that there is a problem here ...because they’re so production focused.’ (in interview, 2022). When faced with such challenges, inspectors try to emphasize key values, such as fairness and consistency but even this can be a challenge, as another inspector admitted, ‘the most difficult [thing] in our job is to be fair, to be straight is a bit complicated when you see these are just people’ (2022). Whilst the legislation and rules can be clear, the importance of being fair was something that many of the inspectors conveyed. This was associated with a commitment to consistency in how they communicated with farmers, drivers, and workers alike.

‘Consistency, that’s what we have pushed as a big thing. Because farmers talk to each other, and consistency is so important. Because it is such a contentious thing – tail biting and tail docking. Farmers are very resistant to change ... they’re afraid of it, they’re afraid to stop tail docking’ (in interview).

This conveys the inspectors’ role in changing attitudes in farming, from the farm to the slaughterhouse where strong traditions are resistant to change. The awareness that farmers talk to each other is a strong influence on the Danish inspectors also, who described the importance of continued communication and calibration between inspectors on welfare issues to ensure a consistent performance of inspection. One inspector described how ‘I hope that he will speak to his neighbours to spread the message that it’s not so bad getting an unannounced visit’. (2022)

This reveals a central tension in the work of inspectors, as one inspector put it, ‘we *don’t advise them, we guide them*’ (2022). However, later they used the term ‘counsel’ in reference to the relationship with the farmer. In Ireland, the relationship was described more colloquially as ‘we don’t advise them, but I’ll tell them what I see down the road, and what has worked on other farms’ (2022). In France, Martin, who has worked as an inspector for 23 years, put it in this way, ‘So now we are not allowed to give advice. I say to the farmers, I can’t give you advice, but I will give you my opinion (the other inspectors laugh at this) ...’ This conflict at the heart of the work of inspection means that inspectors in France described themselves as the ‘police of agriculture’, which Martin admitted was not the kind of relationship he wanted with farmers when he started in the job. This led another veterinary inspector with three years’ experience, to conclude that ‘there are two ways to do it... You tell them what’s wrong because it’s not your job to change things. Or, you have to work with them... and it will be complicated but my work is more meaningful, I can see all the things I do are making a difference.’

4.5 Seeing the Same Way

Across the four countries, inspectors shared insights as to the challenge of seeing the same way, whether this is during a farm inspection or at slaughter where inspectors are working individually but must maintain a consistency in identifying welfare issues. For farm visits, inspectors will check in with each other in the building of their evaluation. One Danish inspector with two years’ experience explains how ‘we like to touch base and decide on the evaluation. It has to be fair for the farmer and farmers talk, so it has to be the same scale that you’re judged. It’s easy in theory but in practice, it can be challenging, so we talk throughout the day and then at the end once more’ (2022). During the inspection, the two inspectors spoke to each other intermittently and then shared the car journey back to the main property to deliver the assessment. This aligned with the approach of the French inspectors. One inspector has been working as an inspector for 11 years and has been training another into the role. He explains how despite the inspectors being open with farmers on the development of the assessment so that there aren’t any nasty surprises at the end of the visit (although Anneberg [5] describes how this might be perceived differently by farmers), the inspectors maintain a discreet dialogue between each other to calibrate their evaluations with one another.

‘It depends because with a senior, you cannot see the same things, you are new, so it depends on what is good and what is a bad farm – the more you go on control, you get confidence. We will never speak in front of the farmer; they will talk about the farm, but we will talk in the car. We won’t do it in front of the farmer so they won’t know that we may not agree.’ (2022)

This touches on another challenge facing inspectors around seeing the same way which another inspector with 23 years’ experience explained how, ‘it’s very important to see the bad to have a different point of view. That’s why if the three of us saw the same animal, we wouldn’t see the same as it depends on our experience’ (2022). In Denmark, the Danish inspectors describe it as ‘*at være ens*’ / to be alike. In the slaughterhouse, an inspector with five years’ experience described how changing who is on duty at the entrance offers a kind of calibration. Thus, if there are some inspectors who have no non-compliances and others who have many, it points to a problem in calibration.

4.6 The Emotional Toll of Animal Welfare Inspection

Inspectors expressed varying degrees of discontent in relation to their working environment. The experiences of isolation were notably mentioned by the newly employed inspectors who shared how they failed to make meaningful connections with inspectors outside their immediate department, as all courses were delivered online due to COVID-19 restrictions. Such connections were noted by other inspectors as important for the role when they faced unusual problems in welfare assessment or needed assistance with legislative documents. There is a real need to provide in person training as much as possible to build and strengthen connections beyond the walls of

Figure 4.6.1: An inspector at slaughter assessing welfare of sows on arrival (© E. Mc Loughlin)

slaughterhouses and offices and the confines of their cars, so that inspectors can collaborate and communicate with one another to increase their job satisfaction and potentially reduce their workload through dialogue on difficult situations. Danish on farm inspectors described routine online meetings as being the norm which helped with calibration on welfare. Polish and Irish inspectors described relations beyond the immediate workplace as arising from maintaining contact with old college friends who are also now involved in inspection. French inspectors had varying degrees of contact beyond their workplace and had similar experiences to that of one Polish inspector who described how she did not have many contacts with other inspectors, as she has only participated in online training. As a French inspector with three years' experience surmised, 'in the beginning of my job, I needed to exchange. You can be very alone in this job. When you speak to others, you can learn a lot.' (2022). The solitary nature of working independently on inspection, particularly experienced by on farm inspectors who typically carry out inspections on their own, unless it is a very large commercial farm, and inspectors in small slaughterhouses is a real challenge for inspectors. The negotiations and compromises that characterize the work of inspection can contribute to an existential dilemma for inspectors encapsulated in the words of one inspector who admitted 'you're never sure if you've done right' (2022).

A number of inspectors expressed a palpable disillusionment with the value of welfare to improve an animals' wellbeing with one inspector admitting 'I mean, I didn't save any animals today. I didn't save a single one. It is cruelty. It is a cruel, cruel world and it is us humans who do it.' Similarly, this same inspector described how seeing animals being shot routinely as part of their working day was something that they had to learn to live with. Whilst similar doubts might erupt in all of us when we reflect on the value of our work, these doubts and experiences of disillusionment reveal the emotional toll of inspection and the importance of providing supports that can be engaged with by inspectors and departments as well as a platform for inspectors to share their experiences in the field, be that on farm, at slaughter, or at transport. As one inspector shared how they needed to make sense of their role at slaughter when they witnessed a sow give birth in the slaughterhouse. 'It was of course a report to the farmer but to stand there with these perfect little pigs who also must die. You have to think a lot about how to live with this, so you don't keep yourself up at night' (2022). Taking the animals and their suffering home with you was noted by another inspector as something that they experience when faced with challenging issues during on farm inspection. In terms of supporting inspectors in their work, the toll of the emotional burden of witnessing suffering is an area warranting further support.

As noted, the isolation is often not simply experienced by inspectors working alone but can be the experience of overseeing welfare in a slaughterhouse where the work of welfare regulation can make workplace relations uncomfortable. One inspector shared the challenging experience of reporting poor stunning technique to the slaughterhouse, saying how 'it was really unpleasant. It's still not great to go down there. I don't look forward to it, but it must be done' (2022).

Figure 4.6.2: An inspector at slaughter assesses the stunning area (© E. Mc Loughlin)

4.7 Power Dynamics

Several inspectors cited a desire to change the welfare of animals as a reason for becoming an inspector but when asked about the power they have to change things, they were a little more ambivalent. French inspectors of farms described how 'we don't have a lot of power, but we have the tools to improve conditions' (2022). This power was demonstrated by a slaughterhouse inspector who issued a series of non-compliances to change the practices of stunning sows, but they noted how it is difficult to stop a worker individually unless there is gross negligence. The issuing of non-compliances as a demonstration of an inspector's welfare standards was a useful way of changing the habits of farmers also, noted another inspector at slaughter. In

order to demonstrate their zero tolerance for tail biting issues, one inspector issued letters to farmers and the incidence of tail biting decreased as a result. Another inspector detailed how they focused on training slaughterhouse operatives to improve the stunning of sows. This approach was beyond their role as regulator, but their training has meant that the stunning of sows is now much more successful. Yet, they also noted that this power to change things is not quick enough when there is a problem, ‘the difficult part is stunning and how to be reactive with operators who are doing bad work. [...] It must be immediate, now, get in and stop things if they are not good’ (2022) but this can be difficult to do without witnessing gross negligence.

Having such a positive impact on welfare no doubt increases job satisfaction but not being empowered in your role can exacerbate feelings of dissatisfaction and disillusionment. In conversations with inspectors, sometimes the power to enforce regulation to the letter is tempered by an awareness of the multifaceted nature of welfare on farms, where inspectors described how personal issues of the farmer are often underlying substandard welfare conditions for animals. As a Polish inspector explained, ‘it is difficult when you see that they have no money’ (2022). I asked the Polish inspectors whether they felt empowered in their role. One inspector replies, ‘it’s difficult when you see they have no money’. Another adds, ‘If they don’t care about the animals, that’s easier’ which prompts the first to add, ‘or if they have alcohol problems’

The inspectors were highlighting a problem that many on farm inspectors identified which was that any non-compliances have a direct economic impact and in turn, a personal impact on the farmer. Whilst many inspectors would counter this with *it is not their responsibility* and *it cannot outweigh animal welfare*, similarly the majority of inspectors empathized with the difficult situation that pig farmers across the European Union are enduring and believed that welfare needed to be balanced within the wider context. Thus, inspectors will try to give the farmers a chance once they get a sense that the farmer is trying to do *right*. As one French inspector noted ‘many farmers want their pigs to be happy. I think that many farmers want to be good, I think profoundly that the majority want to do better, but they have social problems. I think this is a role in the care of animals’ (2022).

Power can extend beyond the slaughterhouses and departments that these inspectors operate in when it comes to the macro influences on their work. Across the four countries, there were not enough inspectors being hired to fulfil the demands of welfare inspection, which points to the macro-politics of animal welfare regulation that is beyond the scope of this report to examine. Nevertheless, where these macro-politics have real impacts on welfare is in the routine prioritization of other areas of evaluation over welfare regulation. Furthermore, the macro politics of animal welfare was especially apparent in both France and Poland but on different ends of the spectrum. The French inspectors all described how important the undercover reports of animal rights organizations to the increased focus and commitment to animal welfare. On the other hand, the outbreak of African Swine Fever in Poland led to a concerted focus on recording and reporting the development of the disease which can result in inspectors doubting the department’s view of welfare. This can extend to the wider political landscape where politicians are believed to be corrupted by their close ties to the farming community. Many inspectors described how close connections between the agricultural lobby groups and government continues to influence animal welfare regulation.

Along with macro political influences on welfare regulation, in conversation with the inspectors of farms in Poland, they described how often their work is unsupported by the chain of command, so as not to worsen

relations between politicians and the farming community. As one inspector detailed, ‘one of the most frustrating things, we go on control, we see bad things, and we give them a chance to change and at the second visit, they didn’t make progress, we decide that they can’t keep pigs anymore but they can appeal and usually, they [the department] decide our decision is wrong and so they can keep pigs... it’s more political because farmers are so angry at the moment with the politicians...’ (2022). Such an experience can heighten feelings of disillusionment when farmers who have been reprimanded are given favourable treatment for political gain. It can also weaken the status of the inspector in the farming community.

4.8 Legislation, Language, and Paperwork

‘They just had room to move around like, that’s another challenge that we have. Stocking density on that directive is... they’re all at the minimum as far as I can see and by the time they get to that weight category, there really is not enough space. They might be within the legal requirement but there’s not enough space! They can’t walk around, they can’t pass by each other and as for lying down! Good luck!’ (2022)

Inspectors identified working with the legislation as a real challenge to their work. The opacity of legislation hinders the implementation of higher standards of welfare, especially regarding tail biting. As we can see here, inspectors must work with a legislative document that sets out minimum standards that in reality do not meet the welfare needs of pigs. This can be especially frustrating for inspectors who are being criticized by the EU for not making progress on tail docking, but who argue that the legislation is not strong enough to implement changes that will make intact tails possible. Working with inflexible black and white legislation in the grey zones of welfare is an experience that a French slaughterhouse inspector of 13 years identified as the main challenge in her work. She explains how it is a challenge to ‘truly respect the legislation to the letter because from one abattoir to another, there are different materials, different animals, nuances and working with black and white legislation when you are working in grey areas is difficult. What is good or bad, the limits. Sometimes, I have to research a lot of literature and legislation in order to figure out certain issues’ (2022). She noted how whilst she enjoys this side of the work, it is time-consuming. Indeed, another inspector shared how, ‘we all know, ok this is terrible, and this isn’t but I’m realizing that I need a background in welfare, like the indicators to assess things... There’s no real help for that, like how do you decide what’s what, where do you draw the line, only your professional judgement but like I could judge one thing and the vet down the road could judge it different’ (2022). This again raises the issue of calibration and seeing the same way as a real area requiring support and resources.

Not surprisingly, the recordkeeping of animal welfare inspection was noted by many as time-consuming and in need of streamlining. An inspector detailed how ‘the worst part is all the paper to fill after control. We have reports that are daily, monthly ... Excel is our friend!... If we had less paper, maybe we would have more time to go on farms. Sometimes, when I go on farms, I think what I have to do after, so I know when I do control with details, I know that I have so much to do after.’ (2022). In the case of Poland, there was a repeated and specific focus on paperwork as it was directly connected to their response to African Swine Fever. Indeed, in conversation with veterinary inspectors at slaughter, they described the most challenging aspect of their job as documentation.

5 Differences between Farm Inspection and Slaughterhouse Inspection

5.1 The Unpredictable Terrain of On-Farm Inspection

There is a heightened demand on emotions in the work of on farm inspection. This is due to the increased travel time and the changing location of work depending on the farm visited but is also exacerbated by the unpredictable nature of farm visits, especially when such a visit is unannounced. As other inspectors have also noted, the task of on farm inspection involves managing the emotions of both yourself and the farmer, along with any other members of the farming team that might join, such as veterinarians or farm managers. The labour of managing the emotions of others as well as managing your own complicate the work of inspection. Such unremunerated and often underappreciated labour has been described by sociologist Arlie Hochschild as contributing to increased feelings of stress and experiences of burnout due to the emotional toll (Hochschild, 2012). Her work focused on the emotional labour of air stewards who must present a calm and positive demeanour to passengers. Indeed, in my own research with slaughterhouse workers, I detail a similar emotional toll as the workers reproduce gendered norms of emotional expression in line with company-defined ways of feeling, where repressing and expressing certain emotions was normalized (Mc Loughlin, 2019). Managing the emotions during on farm visits can include simple acts of sitting with the farmer for a coffee prior to commencing the inspection, to *'give ham ro/calm him'* (2022). It often involves reminding the farmer that the task of inspection is not to catch them out but is in line with legislation.

However, often the emotional labour of inspection is at the point of a welfare issue where inspectors try to understand the logic of poor welfare, be this an animal who is not provided bedding in a hospital pen or why a lame animal has not been separated from the group. Inspectors describe how it is not necessarily the goal to accept the rationale for lapses in care, but to challenge the thinking and change the farmer's perspective (Anneberg et al., 2013).

We enter through a small doorway and a wall of heavy air engulfs me causing my eyes to water. The small room is made smaller by the narrow pathway that the six of us fill where four pens enclose us. It is the pen to the right that the inspectors are focused on rather than the pen to the left and the two to the back. The pen is pulsing with puffed up little pigs who are bounding past one another with excitement and fear at the arrival of people. A chain hangs with a ball and three pigs nuzzle at a piece of timber that is awkwardly stuck in a corner where they have to squeeze past one another to access it. The inspector comments *'they have very little floor space,'* as they scratch the ground and attempt to root. They then ask the room, *'so, what enrichment do we have'*. They peer in as the dozens of pairs of eyes stare back, *'what do we have here, okay timber'*. They watch as only two pigs fight to access the timber that's thrown up against the corner of the pen. *'It should be there, pointing to the middle of the pen.'* They then spot a frayed rope that is now too short for the pigs to access. The farmer comments, *'I underestimated how much pigs like to chew, you put the rope in, and it's gone in a day'*. The inspector points out, *'and isn't that a good thing.'* The farmer retorts, *'well it's the cost'* (2022)

The pressure to maintain good relations and to not be confrontational can heighten feelings of frustration following on farm encounters. The response of the farmer in this encounter is indicative of the experiences of inspectors on farm across the four member states. The economic cost of implementing welfare changes was a habitual retort that, whilst inspectors empathized with the difficult challenges facing pig farmers, was often very difficult for them to accept. As this inspector admitted later, 'I'm talking to the wall because he [the farmer] is complaining about the price of hemp rope... so what if they eat it... that's a good sign... put more in, put more of it in, put something else in. ...but it's not a reason [to not provide enrichment], should you be entitled to keep animals then?'

Figure 5.1.1: An on-farm inspector assessing a sow and piglets (© E. Mc Loughlin)

Amidst this central conflict and despite the emotional toll of inspection, the inspectors across the four countries shared how it was easier to deal with angry farmers because the inspectors could focus on implementing regulation without feeling guilty. Inspectors from all countries recognized how challenging the pig production landscape was at the moment. Some felt sorry for the farmers while others were less compassionate, believing instead that since the farmers are subsidized by Europe, the rules should be followed regardless of the economic costs that were affecting the industry. Either way, it is the *farmer who doesn't care* that poses the greatest challenge to inspectors, as one Danish inspector described, 'it's actually easier to handle a farmer who is really mad because you can just communicate the regulations and you know you are right. It's much harder if they're on the verge of tears and your instinct is to comfort them... but sadness won't change a violation. The worst thing is when one doesn't care... That's hard, if he doesn't really care and if you counsel him and you just know that the next time there is a sick pig, they won't be treated' (2022).

A number of inspectors detailed experiences with farmers who share their financial difficulties, their health problems, and the family issues. As on-farm inspectors are often spending a number of hours with farmers, depending on the size of the farm, this can be quite difficult for the inspectors to deal with. Describing the inspection as a kind of performance where 'you are on', a Danish inspector described how 'it usually takes a full day so you really don't want to get off on the wrong foot because that can make it a long day' (2022). This social aspect of the work was noted by a French inspector, 'If you have a good chat with the farmer, they like to speak about their lives. This is the social aspect of the work. We have to take it into account, the people, if they are in difficulty, why are they here, why do they have disease, there are many aspects to think about.' This provokes me to ask how it influences their assessment of welfare, to which another inspector responds, 'It depends on each personality. Some of our colleagues will be the rules only, while others will be sensitive to it, but you must not allow this to affect you' (2022).

Figure 5.1.2: Two inspectors at on farm inspection (© E. Mc Loughlin)

Nevertheless, inspectors are acutely aware of their role in changing a culture around how pigs are produced by farmers which one inspector described in the following way, ‘These pigs can’t let themselves out, these are intensively reared animals, and they need intensive management, but this has not been fed along in the production in your (farmer’s) training to produce these, they’ve forgotten all that. The pigs will manage themselves they’ve been told, just give them the water and the feed, and let them get on with it. It’s been totally forgotten; production has just told them that the animals will adapt, and it will be fine’ (2022). Inspectors in France,

Ireland, and Poland described how they are part of a cultural shift in shaping how farmers work with pigs. Whilst one French inspector described how it was important for inspectors to communicate changes in legislation, another concluded that, ‘No, they are professionals, they should know, it’s their responsibility to know the changes’ (2022).

Unlike inspectors based at slaughterhouses, on farm inspectors have a varied working week depending on their inspection schedules. Whilst these can be ambitious, leading to several inspectors already admitting that they were behind on the scheduled number of visits for their department. As mentioned above, the varied workload can offer inspectors greater autonomy in their work however, the work of inspection also places inspectors in situations that pose a risk to their health and safety.

‘Nobody knows where I go when I go to an inspection. Because they are unannounced, we can’t put them in the calendar because this is accessible to everyone at the department. I can’t share it with my husband because of personal data law. So nobody knows where you are and that is a problem because you can feel a little unsafe. Like even when we normally show up, there will be another inspector for environment, but we work independently, and often they are gone by the time that I am still working my way through. Normally, visits like this can take a whole day. So that is a problem that we still haven’t figured out – how to be safe when we are out on inspections. Like my husband has no idea where I am’ (2022)

When I spoke to another inspector about this, they dismissed the data protection constraints by telling their partner where they were travelling, as they prioritized their safety. It is also worth noting that across Ireland, Denmark, and Poland, the majority of the on-farm inspectors I spoke to were female. There is a need for a study into the gender-specific challenges of these roles as well as the influence of gender on farmer-inspector and slaughterhouse company-inspector interactions. As mentioned previously, both male and female inspectors reported having experienced abuse in their role and it was noted by several female inspectors that they were demeaned due to their gender and/or age.

5.2 Fighting the Familiar in Slaughterhouse Inspection

The inspectors at slaughter described how they enjoyed the variety of responsibilities that the role offered. In all the slaughterhouses visited, the inspectors would regularly move from ante-mortem to post-mortem. One Danish inspector shared how ensuring that all inspectors who were trained to assess live animal welfare spent time in both ante- and post-mortem was important for job satisfaction as well as calibration (see 4.5 Seeing the Same Way). The everydayness of inspection at slaughterhouses produces a unique set of challenges especially in the maintenance of a good relationship with open dialogue. This is where one inspector emphasized that taking on a role as police officer is not helpful because you need to explain the regulation to them and in order to ensure cooperation, problems should not be seen as failings but rather opportunities to improve (see 4.4 Rapport and Dialogue).

Many inspectors at slaughter described the importance of close relationships with stall workers and some viewed themselves as *working with* the stall workers. However, one Danish inspector described how it is important for inspectors to remember their role, ‘that we oversee the slaughterhouse, we must see the problems and how they must find solutions, but we need to be careful about how we formulate things. See that stall worker there, he would like to be my friend, but we are not friends, it’s so important that there is a distance there.’ This contrasts with another inspector in Denmark who took a more relaxed approach.

‘It is difficult to balance at times, but I have had to say things to the drivers and to the slaughter workers and it is fine. I just tell them if I don’t like something. I explain what I like and don’t like but with some drivers who have been doing it like that for forty years, I can’t change that but while you are here, you can impose on them, so that they behave the way you want them to. We work it out.’ (2022)

Another inspector looked forward to a generational shift as older veterinary inspectors move on making way for inspectors with, what they viewed as, a more progressive understanding of and greater commitment to policing welfare. Across all the slaughterhouses visited, inspectors identified sows as vulnerable to lower standards of welfare due to insufficient research and regulation on sow welfare. One French inspector described the problem with sows as ‘they have more of everything, more lesions, more abscesses, very large lesions, prolapse’ (2022). The unique challenges of working with sows was encapsulated by one Danish inspector who described sows as a ‘different species’ as their behaviour is so different from that of slaughter pigs. I think that this is useful to think about in terms of the specificity of regulation and literature that is required. This inspector went on to explain how sows move totally differently to slaughter pigs, ‘firstly they are adult animals. Sows are more individual and have a totally different flow as adult animals. There’s a history behind them [...] We need law and science to show when stall climate is good enough and when it is too warm. We are really missing the knowledge about this.’ This inspector then elaborated on the problems they face when it comes to the organization of the stalls. They point to a lane bustling with sows, jostling for space as they explain, ‘they are mixed. This is not ok. When they are mixed like this, they fight a lot... but it is necessary.’ They then turn to another lane saying, ‘these came in yesterday, so they have been here for many hours and it’s not ok. They fight so much because they are mixed’ (2022).

Much of the work of inspection is focused on changing the culture of caring for pigs, from transporters to slaughterhouse workers and the importance of research and regulation to these changes is highlighted by inspectors across the four countries. Furthermore, the inspectors at slaughter detailed the ways that they try

to sensitize workers to welfare issues. ‘When I arrived, there was no abuse but there was negligence, and I was really shocked when I arrived. They were not sensitized to animal welfare’ (2022). This inspector explained how they shaped this cultural shift by praising good practice as well as explaining incorrect procedures. Their dialogue with workers and the company reflects the challenges discussed in 4.4 Rapport and Dialogue however, it is insightful to hear how they navigated the challenges of changing the culture of welfare at slaughter.

‘I have spoken to inspectors who say, ‘you shouldn’t do more than your job’ you should just tell them what’s wrong but if I do that, they will just see me as annoying, and you can’t just be in a negative relationship with people you work with everyday’ (2022). Nevertheless, a Polish inspector’s experience illustrates how a good relationship with the slaughterhouse can lead to frustration, as change is slow to come about. ‘They will change it... in the distant future. It’s not that they don’t listen, it’s that there are other things that are more important’ (2022). Similarly, in another French slaughterhouse, an inspector explained how they were not happy with the design of the stalls as there are right-angle turns, but it is something that is slow to change and other changes, specifically around the stunning machinery, are prioritized. Thus, inspectors must find ways to communicate welfare issues and requirements in a way that the importance is appreciated, again to *make welfare make sense* for the company and the workers. From the Danish inspectors working to improve understanding of stocking densities of sows to the French inspectors trying to sensitize the drivers and workers to their herding methods so they are not driving the pigs with force, the inspectors at slaughter must negotiate working relationships with people they face on a daily basis and often this is achieved through establishing your standards early. Indeed, a number of the inspectors were relatively new to the slaughterhouses and so it afforded them the luxury of identifying a welfare issue that they wanted to change whether it was the correct stunning of sows, or better herding methods, or reducing tail biting incidents, or improving stocking density for sows.

Figure 5.2.1: Inspector at slaughter performing transport check (© E. Mc Loughlin)

Inspectors at slaughter strongly communicated the serious challenges they face with transport inspection, from the difficulty to sanction transports operating across regions, to the ambiguity of sanctions in the regulation to their experiences of serious welfare issues arising during transport. As one inspector described, transport is an area that is badly in need of more attention. ‘Transport is more complicated ... it’s not controlled, it’s totally out of control. I think the drivers are doing some things and it’s really hard to control and make them improve. We started to write fines on the transport but there is nothing in regulation to sanction them. I’m trying to make people respect the duration of transport and they don’t. I don’t know what to do. I see in other slaughterhouses that they are not checking transport at all’ (2022).

6 Results and Recommendations

During my time with inspectors, I asked them to define animal welfare in their own words. This question posed a challenge for many inspectors as despite working with this multifaceted, complex, and at times ambiguous concept every day, they found it difficult to put it into their own words. Many noted the harmony between environment and behaviour, where animals have the ability to express natural behaviours, and others emphasized the importance of good physical health, good condition, and good performance. Most noted the direct conflict between industrial farming conditions and the ability of animals to have good welfare. One going so far as to say that they didn't use the term welfare when speaking of pigs in these sorts of conditions, choosing animal protection instead. The fact that so many inspectors identified a tension between farming and animal welfare highlights the importance of their role in minimizing suffering and finding ways to improve the lives of animals on farm and at slaughter. The widespread view amongst inspectors that by definition, animal welfare was difficult to describe when it came to industrially raised pigs also reveals the considerable emotional toll on inspectors who nevertheless must attempt to police animal welfare.

The recent publication of Anneberg & Rousing (2022) was of marked interest to several inspectors. Therefore, regarding recent discussions around EURCAW – Pigs training activities, holding seminars with competent authorities or as part of BTSF training on this topic would be an excellent area to develop for EURCAW – Pigs training activities.

Inspectors appreciate the value of dialogue in learning and training, from the importance of meetings when new regulations are being introduced to the centrality of dialogue in the training up of new colleagues. Thus, in training activities, the facilitation of dialogue should be central to activities. Despite differences in the route to becoming an inspector, the training that inspectors receive mainly involved side-by-side training with a more senior inspector. Such an experience drew on the background of the experienced inspector with a view to making possible a 'seeing the same way' across inspectors. Seeing the same way is not a science but an art that requires calibration which inspectors in Denmark highlighted as essential throughout the career of an inspector. As a new starter, seeing the same way was described as a process of unlearning and relearning by one French inspector who was training another into the role. Despite the newly hired inspector having a background in horse husbandry, his 22 years' experience as a policeman was a challenge. The inspector training him in described how, 'his police experience [led him] to look for the wrong side, that was something, that it's also important to find both the good and the bad' (2022).

It is important to highlight that calibration is not always dialogical and peer centered. Calibration can also be on an individual level through the kinds of cases that inspectors are faced with. This kind of calibration assists in the task of what inspectors call 'where do you draw the line' on good and bad welfare. Indeed, in Poland, when I asked one inspector for her initial thoughts on the farm inspection, her response reflected a contextual evaluation, rather than a specific assessment of the farmer's compliance with legislation as she said, 'to me, it was okay because I know worse things can happen' (2022). One French inspector described how experiencing a lot of bad welfare can similarly calibrate your expectations, 'when you're seeing a lot of bad treatment or [animals] in a bad state, you reconsider your perception of what is good or badly treated. It's very important to see the bad to have a different point of view' (2022). This highlights the logic behind

several inspectors raising the need for welfare examples in training that include both the good and the bad, and the grey area in between.

Finally, calibration requires peer exchange so that poor welfare issues become sensitized for inspectors. During one field visit, I noticed a significant number of sows who were emaciated with several of them unable to walk correctly due to overgrown crescent-shaped toenails. Later, the inspector I was accompanying shared how my reactions made her reflect on where she set the line on welfare. Thus, whilst understanding that welfare evaluation involves compromise, calibration should similarly draw on the insights and responses of those newly qualified, potentially more sensitized, inspectors as a way to drive welfare forward. Nevertheless, inspector welfare is central to job satisfaction and mental health and there must be a balance between accepting things as they are and wanting things to improve, otherwise inspectors can face increased feelings of skepticism about their role as well as the concept of welfare. This can be exacerbated by fears that inspectors are evaluating areas differently, which can heighten feelings of frustration.

‘We started to write fines on the transport but there is nothing in regulation to sanction them. I’m trying to make people respect the duration of transport and they don’t. I don’t know what to do. I see in other slaughterhouses that they are not checking transport at all. Last time, ten pigs died in an accident when the truck overturned. I did a warning, and the company did not like it, but ten pigs died! But in another part of the country, something similar happened and nothing happened’ (2022).

6.1 Familiarity with EURCAW

Out of 26 participants, only three were familiar with EURCAW-Pigs and two of these were working at a senior administrative level. Thus, this research demonstrates that EURCAW-Pigs must invest time, resources, and energy into building connections with inspectors on the ground. Whilst a cascade effect through head offices is one way, a more direct engagement with inspectors can offer key insights into the nature of their work, the challenges they face, and inform EURCAW-Pigs’ work programme in the coming years. This can be achieved through collaboration with training centers for veterinary inspectors in the respective member states with a view to identifying key contact points, collaboration with BTSF courses, and direct contact to local offices. To overcome language barriers, individuals identified as key contact points may assist in disseminating EURCAW-Pigs as a resource for inspectors and may also provide a feedback system to EURCAW-Pigs.

6.2 Training Needs and Resources

Whilst there was a widespread interest in and curiosity about materials in the form of videos, the demanding nature of inspections, from planning to implementation and follow-up means that inspectors may not have time to spend watching videos, or indeed may be too jaded from online meetings that have become the norm. However, one inspector in France noted how a podcast would be useful and would be especially useful for inspectors who are spending considerable time in their cars either travelling to and from inspection sites or in their daily commute. There is real potential here to develop a podcast based on interviewing inspectors about their work, the challenges involved, as well as opportunities to cover topics relevant to their work from welfare evaluation to communication. Additionally, several inspectors noted how interesting and beneficial

it would be to learn about how other inspectors have brought a welfare case through from identifying the problem to legislative action and the conclusion.

In Ireland, one inspector described how they would appreciate an individual dedicated to training to work with inspectors from the outset, as they noted that side-by-side training and mentorship, whilst very positive, can sometimes feel like you should reach a position where you no longer need assistance. A dedicated trainer operating throughout the regional offices could provide an access point for continued development and ongoing training. A similar idea was also suggested by a newly employed French inspector who described how having individuals who were specialized in certain areas of legislation or work procedures could be useful to establish in veterinary offices in slaughterhouses to ease the burden of self-directed study. This concept could also be extended to regional offices conducting farm inspection. Additionally, an emphasis on exchange between colleagues was noted by all inspectors as being essential to making their lives easier. These are changes that could be implemented across the departments to cultivate a culture of open dialogue and a commitment to calibration rather than EURCAW – Pigs' activities. However, the *Questions 2 EURCAW – Pigs* contribute to this culture of open dialogue as they provide an access point to experts and could be further promoted.

6.3 Differences between countries

Many inspectors across Ireland, Poland, and France noted that there can be differences across the regions that can be a challenge to enforcement and regulation and also be reflected in overall welfare levels in regions. An inspector with over 20 years' experience in France explained how 'There are differences in different departments in inspection so here, we do more unannounced visits, whereas if you tell them ahead, the welfare is going to be much better' (2022). This view has been documented elsewhere by Ceccantini (2017) who describes how veterinary inspectors interviewed on obstacles to pig welfare in France highlighted the challenges due to 'a departmental disparity

Figure 6.3.1: Inspector assessing welfare of weaners (© E. Mc Loughlin)

through which practices are accepted in certain regions and not in others' Differences between regions was cited by Polish inspectors as a real challenge to their work as it led to communication difficulties across regions and increased their duties as they lacked the benefit of a coordinated system of enforcement. Regional differences sparked a curiosity in how inspections are carried out in other countries. One inspector noted, 'sometimes we are saying that in Eastern Europe, that regulations are not applied as much, that we are doing it right, but it would be better to see how these places are doing it.' Whilst a Polish inspector with 16 years' experience noted how, 'people come here to see and I never had the opportunity to go to Denmark for example and see how they do things. [...] like the instruction says one thing and reality says different... we'd like to see how they do it in other countries' (2022). Inspectors noted how visits were clearly the most

insightful but also were positive towards the idea of short webinars or videos on inspections in different European contexts.

Several inspectors noted how beneficial it would be to learn about how other inspectors have brought a welfare case through from identifying the problem to legislative action and the conclusion. Inspectors often pointed out how they were interested in how other member states carry out inspection because they are all working with the same European legislation. As one inspector described, ‘it would be interesting to know how they do it because it’s the same system and to see how they work with interpretation, is it the same across the different countries’ (2022).

In terms of learning from different countries, the intact tails initiative in Ireland is a good example of how such cross-pollination of ideas could unfold. This initiative is being trialed and involved a considerable degree of planning, training, and implementation. Having spoken to coordinators of the visits and training as well as accompanied inspectors on these visits, other European member states could greatly benefit from learning about the experiences of Irish inspectors both in terms of communication and enforcement. The visits are small-scale in that the veterinary inspectors are only assessing two pens across four visits that assess the risk factors for tail biting and with each visit, it is required that the farmer address these risk factors. The initiative requires good dialogue with farmers as inspectors attempt to educate farmers on the multifactorial causes of tail biting. One inspector detailed how, ‘we have to educate them about that... it’s normal because we are two generations away from people who reared pigs with intact tails, and I suppose the production has just kind of normalized the current situation for them... and they can say that this is the normal’ (2022). Whilst I have spoken to a Danish inspector who felt that the differences between countries was too great to see the benefit of shared experiences, Danish farmers continue to dock 95% of tails and insights from the Irish initiative could be directly beneficial to other member states as a point of collaboration and development across national borders. In turn, the very real threat that ASF poses to European countries is another area where there are opportunities for inspectors to learn from member states like Poland in their response to ASF, the logistics of containing disease, and the paperwork behind processing claims.

6.4 Systems and Data Management

Inspectors in Poland expressed an interest in more digitalization of the procedures and there is an opportunity here to develop resources for data management and potentially draw on insights from other member states, where digitalization has successfully been incorporated into inspection. As one inspector said ‘so even if we talk about a system we use for samples, we have it, but another part of Poland doesn’t. We are not always sending the same information and then the problem is when we have to talk about inspection that our tools are totally different... the paperwork and systems cannot communicate with one another’ (2022). Whilst some paperwork was noted by inspectors as necessary, certain inspectors appeared to be dealing with administrative and bureaucratic tasks that were perceived as a form of surveillance (of inspectors) rather than regulation of pig welfare. As one inspector put it, it is ‘a record of what we do’ (2022).

6.5 Working with Other Inspectors

A Community of Practice that facilitated the exchange of ideas and experiences was well-received by the majority of inspectors. Those who were hesitant cited a lack of time to engage with such a resource as a

barrier but recognized the value of exchange. All participants felt that visiting both inspiring and challenging examples of farms and slaughterhouses in other member states would be especially beneficial for their understanding of welfare assessment. I would add that more initiatives like this would boost job satisfaction and collaboration across borders. For example, an Irish inspector involved in the intact tails initiative specifically mentioned how a visit to Finland to see how they have successfully implemented the European legislation on a ban of tail docking would be of enormous benefit to implementing real change at home.

Connected to learning from other countries, on farm inspectors in Denmark participated in regular meetings with other inspectors where such meetings enabled discussion of recent experiences, inspiring examples, and challenges. Such a concept could be utilized in other member states to address issues of isolation as well as producing greater opportunities for peer dialogue and calibration (see 4.5 Seeing the Same Way and 4.6 The Emotional Toll of Animal Welfare Inspection).

7 Conclusion

When I asked one inspector about the main challenges facing veterinary inspectors, they explained how it goes back to the ethos of the veterinary profession, ‘the ethos of the job is to promote the welfare of the animals,’ going on to say that they would like to see inspectors ‘take this on in a more meaningful way’ (2022). They argued that more veterinary inspectors need to be pushing for higher standards of welfare in the pig industry, specifically mentioning the docking of tails and stalling of sows as key issues that must be highlighted and challenged. However, in assessing welfare in farming and slaughter environments that are totally unnatural for these pigs, many inspectors expressed a dissatisfaction with their ability to improve the lives of pigs, which often led to the work going home with the inspectors. One inspector admitted, ‘you kind of think about it. I went home and thought, should we have done that differently’ (2022).

So much of the work of inspection is accepting the necessity of the way the system is and finding ways to live within it, so that your work makes a positive impact. As this inspector noted, ‘legislation allows for it and I can disagree with it and I can feel it’s not right, but I can’t tell him [the farmer] to do anything different... You have to work with what’s going on... I don’t agree with it’ (2022). From the French and Irish inspectors who have identified key points of welfare to improve at slaughter to the Danish inspectors who work hard to calibrate their assessments to the Polish who want to improve the system so that the paperwork does not detract from time with farmers, the burden of economics, the constraint of necessity, and the opacity of legislation can be an emotional and psychological drain on inspectors. Therefore, spending time with inspectors to understand how they find ways to make their work matter beyond the paperwork is essential to comprehending their challenges and the needs that arise from them.

7.1 Key Action Points

- Interview-based podcast discussing topics of inspection with inspectors discussing challenges and how to address them, on farm, at transport, and at slaughter
- Direct contact to the regional offices as well as the head offices to ensure that EURCAW-Pigs’ work cascades through the ecosystem of inspection. There is an option here to identify a contact person who is willing to collaborate with EURCAW which would also assist with language barriers.

- Literature on sow welfare, indicators of fitness at transport, stunning methods, transport regulations, and conditions of housing pigs in stalls at lairage both overnight and for shorter periods – such as research on temperature, stocking density, and mixing. I visited three slaughterhouses where they were slaughtering sows, either only sows or a number of sows a day/a week. Across all three sites, inspectors complained that further research into sow welfare was needed so that they could penalize non-compliances and identify who is responsible for poor welfare or critical issues.
- In all literature and resource development, the good, the bad, and the ambiguous has to be provided in order to cultivate engagement and discussion at a local level
- Comprehensive study of how inspection is performed across all European countries as all inspectors expressed an interest in understanding how inspection is implemented in other European countries.
- More fieldwork focused on transport checks as these were not possible to fully incorporate into this project, but transport was consistently mentioned by inspectors as an area associated with significant risks to welfare.
- Ethnographic research into the experiences of female inspectors to produce resources and supports that are tailored to addressing gender discrimination.
- Greater provision of materials and literature on conflict resolution, resilience training, and communication strategies. There is a need to provide support for inspectors so the doubts and frustrations they encounter can be eased through a network of literature, resources, and shared experiences.

7.2 Looking to the Future

As noted above, a number of inspectors expressed an interest in further literature on transport and assessing welfare at transport. However, whilst the project was initially intended to incorporate the experiences of inspectors at transport also, this proved to be too time-consuming to organize successfully and meaningfully within the tight schedule. Therefore, the experiences of inspectors working with transport mainly reflects inspections of transporters for under eight hours journey time where the inspection is carried out at the slaughterhouse. Yet despite a limited amount of data, transport was repeatedly

Figure 7.2.1: Inspector at slaughter (© E. Mc Loughlin)

mentioned as a challenging area to regulate. Therefore, there is a serious need for more fieldwork with inspectors specifically working with both long and short haul transport and those operating at export facilities and rest stops. This reflects the experiences of inspectors in this study whilst insights from this area would

complement the upcoming BTSF focus on transport in their training activities and as such, would enhance the possibilities for collaboration between BTSF and EURCAW-Pigs.

Furthermore, such a collaboration with inspectors is vital to ensuring that EURCAW-Pigs not only produces literature and resources for use by inspectors but that as a resource in itself, EURCAW-Pigs must be responsive to the experiences and needs of inspectors. Activities like ‘Inspector @ Work’ and Inspiring Examples are important in such a relationship whilst fieldwork focused on the reality of inspection, the challenges of bureaucracy and legislation, and the emotional demands of the role must be incorporated into future activities so that EURCAW-Pigs is both *a resource for* **and** *a reflection of* the work of inspection in Europe. Thus, continued collaboration with these inspectors as well as further research in other European countries is vital for building and sustaining a connection to inspectors and the challenges they face in their work. Throughout my time with inspectors, I have witnessed how they are often left with mixed feelings as they choose the battles to win and accept the necessity of compromise on a daily basis. Such repeated negotiation of mixed feelings is intrinsic to understanding how inspectors can be assisted in terms of resources, literature, and training activities. As one inspector put it, ‘My scepticism has changed to cynicism over the years, nearly to the point of giving up.’ In a follow-up email correspondence, this inspector urged a reflection on the following, ‘Why is it not obvious to those well qualified experts that the current regulations with the derogations do not, and will not work? Why send out individual veterinary inspectors in member states to try and change the world farm by farm? Ultimately, why do we allow pigs to be kept in these conditions when the EU can change it by regulation?’ (Personal correspondence, 2022). This report has examined the challenges facing inspectors in the field and I hope that it shows how a continued negotiation of mixed feelings can take an emotional and physical toll on inspectors who are tasked with the unenviable task of *changing the world farm by farm*.

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8.2 Note on the text

Anonymity of participants was assured however in the specific countries; inspectors were aware to some degree of who I was joining due to the snowball approach I employed to identify potential participants. Therefore, in order to further protect identities, at times the excerpts provide limited details to guarantee anonymity without sacrificing valuable insights. Any names used are pseudonyms.

About EURCAW-Pigs

EURCAW-Pigs is the first European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare. It focuses on pig welfare and legislation, and covers the entire life cycle of pigs from birth to the end of life. EURCAW-Pigs' main objective is a harmonised compliance with EU legislation regarding welfare in EU Member States. This includes:

- for pig husbandry: Directives 98/58/EC and 2008/120/EC;
- for pig transport: Regulation (EC) No 1/2005;
- for slaughter and killing of pigs: Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009.

EURCAW-Pigs supports:

- inspectors of Competent Authorities (CA's);
- pig welfare policy workers;
- bodies supporting CA's with science, training, and communication.

Website and contact

EURCAW-Pigs' website www.eurcaw-pigs.eu offers relevant and actual information to support enforcement of pig welfare legislation.

Are you an inspector or pig welfare policy worker, or otherwise dealing with advice or support for official controls of pig welfare? Your question is our challenge! Please, send us an email with your question and details and we'll get you in touch with the right expert.

info.pigs@eurcaw.eu

www.eurcaw-pigs.eu

Services of EURCAW-Pigs

- **Legal aspects**
European pig welfare legislation that has to be complied with and enforced by EU Member States;
- **Welfare indicators**
Animal welfare indicators, including animal based, management based and resource based indicators, that can be used to verify compliance with the EU legislation on pigs;
- **Training**
Training activities and training materials for inspectors, including bringing forward knowledge about ambivalence in relation to change;
- **Good practices**
Good and best practice documents visualising the required outcomes of EU legislation;
- **Demonstrators**
Farms, transport companies and abattoirs demonstrating good practices of implementation of EU legislation.

Partners

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- Wageningen Livestock Research, The Netherlands
- Aarhus University, Denmark
- Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Germany